

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION. TECHNOLOGY OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION STRATEGY DEVELOPMENT. A BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE BENEFITS.

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Abstract: The article shows the specific features of strategic management of the educational system in modern conditions, their understanding allows for the development of viable solutions. Based on the analysis, the author of the article determined the sequence of evolutionary series in the development of the management system. And on this basis, a new approach to education management is based - "management by tasks" is a special form of strategic approach to education management and is most suitable for the genesis of the management system. The argument of this article is adequate modern conditions for the development of the education management system. The author substantiates this with a number of cases that are objective today. Thus, the level of setting and solving problems can be considered as a parametric characteristic of the study of the evolution of educational management, which reveals the essence of the management strategy in a certain period of evolution.

Key words: Strategic learning, forecasting, management system, cybernetic aspect, semiotic aspect, management of the educational system.

Strategic learning management processes

In the theory of educational management, its uniqueness is manifested in different approaches to management classified according to certain criteria. These approaches determine the essence of the management process and can serve as a subject of analysis in the process of historical-pedagogical research of its evolution, perform the function of qualifying the leading paradigm of this management. Undoubtedly, each of them brought a certain benefit at one or another historical stage in the process of formation of management. However, each approach has certain limitations according to the conceptual model of historical and pedagogical studies on the development of the research management system presented in the previous paragraph. In the process of studying the evolution of education management in the region, we put forward the hypothesis that task management as a special form of strategic approach to management can be considered as an integrative criterion of this analysis.

The analysis of works in the field of strategic management made it possible to reveal the essence and specific features of such management, to determine the main features of the concept of "strategy" and its connection with the concepts of "development" and "forecasting". . In education, the concepts of "strategy", "strategic management (management)" were introduced to show the differences between operational management and management, where the main focus is on external factors. However, the authors put different emphasis on defining this essence. Therefore, G. Mintzberg, J. Quinn, S. Goshals view strategic management as "the process of determining and establishing the connection between the system and its environment, which consists of the implementation of selected goals and attempts to achieve the desired state of relations." allows for effective and efficient interaction with the environment through the allocation of resources. The difference between strategic and operational management is manifested as follows: in setting the goal; in determining the main factors of building a management system; consideration of time factors; in evaluating management efficiency, etc. For example, if operational management connects the search for reserves with the internal potential of the educational system, strategic management is directed to the external environment and the search for new funds. competition.

- Summarizing the above, strategic management can be described as a continuous process aimed at long-term survival due to timely changes, flexible response to external environmental impulses and disturbances, reliance on human potential.

- Strategic management The educational system has its own characteristics, which are determined by:

- The field of education has been and remains one of the most innovative fields, which mainly determines the effectiveness of innovative activities in other fields;

- educational system This is a global system of open, flexible, individualized, creative knowledge, continuous education throughout a person's life, production innovations in the field of education (teaching and teaching technologies, methods and methods) and represents a (new) unit of management innovation. economic mechanisms in the field of education, new organizational structures, institutional forms);

- managing the development of the educational system, providing the system of influences on the introduction of technological, pedagogical, organizational innovations, providing the necessary trends, anticipating and

eliminating possible crises and contradictions, maintaining the integrity of the system refers to the organization in such a way as to provide;

- strategic management of the educational system has an innovative nature and is associated with strategic risks, including various political events, unexpected state laws and regulations, the inconsistency between social demands on the educational system and its real resources includes risk management.

The use of the strategic paradigm in the study of the development of the management of the educational system, in our opinion, allows sorting out not only the leading trends of this development, but also the most important trends. Management activities specific topics.

Education management systems considered in various studies (primarily regional) can be called "goal-based" and "result-based" management systems. The analysis of management by objectives shows that such management often turns into a process of setting goals without taking into account real resources, achieved results, and management by results mainly takes into account only pragmatic results, that is, the so-called "effective goals" . it also does not fully reflect the understanding of educational management as the interaction of actors or the management of activities.

In the context of the paradigm of strategic management of education, L.S. based on the general theory of activity presented in his works. Vygotsky, V.V. Davydova, E.V. Ilyenkova, A.N. Leontiev, S.L. Rubinstein, G.P. Shchedrovitsky and others, we identified a special form that best corresponds to the genesis of the education management system in the region - "task management". By "tasks" we understand the conditions of the future result (goal) model, the means of achieving the result, the methods of using funds, the conditions for the implementation of activities and the criteria for evaluating the future result. . In this sense, "task" can be seen as a synonym of "strategy". It does not change until the need is satisfied or there is a need to switch to another alternative (change strategy). Completing the formulation of the task leads the subject of the action to the implementation of the strategy, i.e. to the "executive" stage. It is from this moment that he gets the opportunity to move to the real use of the selected tools and methods, that is, to move from the "internal" preparation process to the real "external" activity, to the real practice of satisfaction. initial need. In the activity approach aspect, there are tasks related to the analysis, study, definition, development and testing of management decisions. The way to the goal is found by solving these problems. S.L. Rubinstein and A.N. Leontiev clearly interpreted the meaning of the task as the unity of the goal and the conditions for its

achievement. When the conditions for achieving the goal change, but the goal itself remains, the task also changes. In the conditions of the implementation of the principle of activity in educational management, the result is not the educational system, but the result of the approach to the system, i.e. the quality of tasks set by the system. In this case, we can talk about the evolution of educational management in terms of production quality. educational objectives. The question arises as to what the levels of this production might be. Let's try to theoretically justify the problem under consideration, distinguishing its cybernetic and semiotic aspects. Let's try to explain the problem theoretically.

Cybernetic aspect

Despite the fact that some authors do not share the transfer of control interpretations in cybernetics to management, we believe that it is still necessary to refer to this theory in terms of the problem under study. From the point of view of R.F. Abdeev, the control mechanism appeared and developed in the process of evolution, it has transitions from the bottom to the top. Physical interaction of objects and elementary forms of reflection (stage 0) were a prerequisite here.

Thus, R.F. Abdeev distinguishes three stages:

I - the simplest closed loop with feedback at the level of a traditional regulator (homeostasis), with a reaction only to current influences (a goal appears - self-preservation);

II - intermediate, with the nature of influencing the program change while maintaining the stability of the management link;

III is the control mechanism of self-organizing systems, which is distinguished by the presence of the II cycle of OS and memory. In the second round, useful information from the I scheme: this information is collected, experience, knowledge is formed, synthesized into certain structures, the level of organization of the system, activity and survivability increase.

Everyday practice shows that development processes in human society consist of very different management and (or) self-management schemes. Each such scheme is a target information and management process, consisting of a managed object and a management subject (management link), with direct and reverse information communication. closes with Regardless of the differences in features (multi-level, specific areas of activity, etc.), the structure of this mechanism is the same. This also applies to management. social systems including education.

Semiotic aspect

The method of obtaining attributive knowledge as the formation of a socially significant standard, the procedure for comparing any specific object of a certain class with it, and determining the result of comparison using the form of a sign is related to the corresponding operation of systems. - called a collective scheme. This can be compared to the simplest closed loop presented by R.F. Abdeev.

The next stage in the development of educational management is associated with the emergence of private schemes that correspond to the collective scheme with the help of appropriate schemes (private schemes are justified by the social need to correct the collective scheme). An analogy of this stage can be an intermediate scheme that has a programmatic change of the nature of the control unit's effect on the object, while maintaining its stability.

The next stage of development (self-organizing systems management mechanism by R.F. Abdeev) is characterized by the implementation and regulation of activities according to the organizational scheme, i.e. the main focus is not on the design of the activity itself, but on the coordination and organization of the interaction of many private schemes within a certain collective scheme (such as the management of individual development trajectories).

Thus, the level of setting and solving problems can be considered as a parametric characteristic of the study of the evolution of educational management, which reveals the essence of the management strategy in a certain period of evolution.

The following literature was used in the development of materials:

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